

THE ESSENCE OF DETERMINING PSYCHOLOGICAL GOALS AND OBJECTIVES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT THINKING ESSENCE OF DETERMINATION

Yakubova Barno Baxtiyorovna

Senior Lecturer of the "Department of Languages and Humanities",
Andijan State Technical Institute

b.yakubova 1990@gmail.com,+99877-037-00-57

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of students' intellectual abilities, problems encountered in educational activities and ways to eliminate them, the essence of defining pedagogical goals and objectives, designing training sessions, modern methods used in educational activities, the content of organizing training sessions, and modern requirements for them. The essence, design of training sessions, modern methods used in training sessions, the content of training organization, and modern requirements for it are discussed.

Keywords: knowledge, skills, qualification, competence, technology, education, science, production, psychological goal, teacher, upbringing.

It should be particularly emphasized that without setting clear objectives for educational sessions, it is impossible to achieve the desired outcome, and without specific goals, it is unfeasible to implement the assigned tasks and attain practical results. The outcome will mirror the goal. Only when educators set a clear ultimate objective do they seek ways to achieve it. When establishing goals, it is necessary to analyze needs and problems, focus the objectives on significant issues, set serious and specific aims, formulate goals in a way that allows for measuring their achievement, set motivating objectives, ensure that all activity participants are aware of the goals, and adhere to the requirement that the aim of each session aligns with the overall program objective. [1.144]

To formulate the goal of a lesson based on these requirements, the teacher must know what needs to be achieved by the end of the lesson and which indicators should be used to measure the results. Currently, there are many shortcomings in defining goals, which include: setting excessive goals, goals that do not match the scale of available training resources, formality in setting them, frequent changes of goals during the training process, and ambiguities in their formulation.

We recommend the following algorithm for setting training objectives: assessing existing problems and identifying the main ones, clearly formulating these problems, determining the stages and sequence of their solution, clearly formulating intermediate results when performing each stage, assessing which of these stages can be precisely implemented within the framework of the training, and then formulating the training objective.[2.60]

Modern research shows that the goal in the pedagogical process is a decisive factor in the teacher's integration of all pedagogical tools into one system. Goal-setting is an important condition of the teacher's activity, allowing to model the trajectory of the individual's activity, to implement personal development.

The idea of defining the goal in the planning and implementation of training is fundamental in improving the quality and effectiveness of the educational process. Defining the goal determines not only the activities of the students, but also the teachers, as well as the entire educational institution, which allows determining the appropriate teaching technologies and the system of criteria for evaluating the results obtained. [3.136]

Defining the pedagogical goal emerges as the most basic professional competence of a teacher in a modern approach to education. They are the teacher's ability to solve important problems, systematize the process of defining goals, think creatively, analyze pedagogical phenomena, set well-founded pedagogical goals, choose means of their implementation, and evaluate personal activity.

The problem of defining pedagogical goals has attracted the attention of many foreign scientists: in the system of general education, didactics, upbringing. The development of the idea of defining the goal in didactics makes a great contribution to the concept of problem-based learning, based on the logic of the general course of the educational process and the effective development of the thinking process.

Research by L.V.Bayborodova, N.V.Kuzmina, A.K.Markova is devoted to the problem of defining goals in the pedagogical process. O.E. Lebedev studied the theoretical foundations of defining the pedagogical goal in the education system. V.G.Gladkikh analyzed the problems of defining pedagogical goals in education, and the theoretical foundations for defining pedagogical goals in the activities of a leader were created. N.Ya.Korostleva identified the specific features of defining the pedagogical goal as an object of management. [4.228]

Analysis of the definition of the pedagogical goal shows that there are different approaches to understanding its essence. In the concepts of some scholars, the specific features of defining the pedagogical goal as a public institution are highlighted in the design of education, the construction of the pedagogical process, and the professional and practical activity of the teacher.

The definition of a pedagogical goal is understood by scientists as follows: the process of correctly defining and setting the goals of pedagogical activity, which reflects the teacher's ability to plan public goals with their own goals and their interaction with students, as well as the selection of specific goals and effective methods for achieving them; the ability to jointly use the goals of society and one's own goals, and then offer them to students for discussion; the process of the main social goals of education, determined by the social order based on specific goals of the content of education (education, upbringing, development), academic subjects, academic topics, classes; not only setting, developing, and using educational goals, but also diagnosing the disclosure of goals, making corrections to them in the future. [5.50]

According to N.V. Kuzmina, the goal-defining stage is characterized by the teacher transforming the state goals facing the education system into pedagogical goals and, through the selection of means for their implementation, transforming students from an object of education into a subject of self-education, independent learning, and self-development.

Setting educational, upbringing, and developmental goals in the learning process creates favorable conditions for the assimilation of knowledge and the formation of necessary personal qualities. In the process of acquiring knowledge in educational activities, views and spiritual qualities are also formed, that is, the unity and interdependence of these functions is observed. [6.4] Understanding the interconnectedness of a teacher's teaching functions allows

them to creatively set and solve the educational, upbringing, and developmental tasks of training sessions.

The goals set in the training session help to search for methods in carrying out educational work. The teacher's ability to implement these tasks in the learning process ensures their creative and pedagogical skillful work. The identification of these goals in the learning process creates good conditions for the assimilation of knowledge and the formation of necessary personal qualities. [7.41] In the process of acquiring knowledge in educational activities, views and spiritual qualities are also formed, that is, the unity and interdependence of these functions are observed.

Another aspect of the content of the educational function of teaching is the assimilation of educational material. The achievement of this goal depends on the nature of the knowledge being imparted to students. The more clearly this goal is defined and the more it corresponds to the materials obtained during the training sessions, the easier it will be to choose teaching methods in this process. General educational goals provide students with knowledge, skills, and abilities in a certain system, develop their oral or written speech, effectively use the content of subjects to correctly understand reality, apply educational materials, provide students with the necessary knowledge, information, skills, and abilities to continue independent continuous education in the future, select educational content and structure it, review and plan new educational materials, identify basic concepts, and transition from general problems in educational materials to solving specific problems.

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The educational goal of teaching is to form positive views and beliefs, morality, willpower, and emotions in students. In each lesson, the teacher carries out a certain aspect of the educational task in the process of teaching educational materials. The formation of worldview, moral qualities of the individual, emotions, willpower is a continuous process, which cannot be divided into clearly limited parts. [8.16]

The results of the educational goal are not as specific and precise as the results of the educational goal. The educational goal is realized differently in students. Studying any educational material influences the development of students, the logic of thinking in it, and the motivation to learn and study. These goals include education, connecting theory with practice, fostering interest in studying sciences, cultivating a culture of correct thinking, fostering intellectual, physical, moral, aesthetic, labor, and professional development, fostering ideological and patriotic human qualities, and the ability to continue independent learning in various subjects. [9.10]

The implementation of the developmental goal of education is analogous to the implementation of the educational goal. The most important thing in the implementation of the developmental task, as in the implementation of the educational goal, is the formation of students' aspirations for it. It is impossible to set and implement the task of developing logical

methods of analysis and synthesis, the ability for abstract thinking, and the formation of active and independent thinking in one lesson. [10.12]

The clarified learning objectives must first be determined through which control work they will be tested. Test and control works are selected based on the objective. Selective control is applied separately for each goal. For example, separate control work must be found for the first set goal, and separate control work for achieving the next goal. All control works are summarized and the final assessment is announced. For example, if goal 1 is defined as memorizing a definition, it is required to recite it from memory. If the 2nd goal is to teach the practical application of the formula, then it is required to apply it in practice. If the 3rd goal is to apply the formula in an unconventional case, then a corresponding example is selected and it is required to work on it.

Consequently, as many control works as the goals have been clarified will need to be developed. Thus, a harmony is created between the goal and control work. When selecting control works, the nature of the objective must be taken into account. Clearly defined goals facilitate verification. Various types of tests can be used in control works..

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